

ISic3534

I.Sicily inscription 3534

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis at the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory 4138

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR033626

1. M (arcus) Va [lerius---]

2. P,ø m (ptina) [---]

Edition: PHI313658

1. M (arcus) □ Va [lerius (?) — —]

2. Pom (ptina) [— — — — —]

3. [— — — — —]

4. [— — — — —]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284781

EDR 033626

EDCS 14805808

PHI 313658

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 27 undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 85 no.9

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